

Faunistic researches on spiders (Araneae) in Poland: a historical background and perspectives

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ABSTRACT. Faunistic researches on spiders (Araneae) in Poland: a historical background and perspectives.

This paper presents the history of research and summarizes the faunistic data on spiders occurring in Poland. An analysis of the degree of knowledge of the national fauna was also carried out. A summary concerning the number of species found in particular zoogeographical regions was presented. The current state of knowledge and perspectives of the development of faunistic studies in Poland are also discussed. Moreover, this paper contains a short description of the project „Araneae of Poland” currently available at the website zbioryprzyrodnicze.web.amu.edu.pl.

KEY WORDS: Araneae, citizen science, faunistics, Poland.

INTRODUCTION

Faunistic studies on spiders have a long tradition in Poland, dating back to the early 19th century. The first comprehensive work on the arachnofauna of our country is WEIGEL's paper (1806), which provides generalized information about 10 species occurring in Silesia. However, the most significant contributions to faunistic research on spiders in the first half of that century were works of SEIDEL (1848, 1849) and MENGE (1843, 1850), who presented data on over 150 species. Currently, the number of faunistic data from our country has significantly increased, encompassing information from over 1000 publications in various publications, both Polish and foreign (PRÓSZYŃSKI & STARĘGA 1971, ROZWAŁKA 2021). Compiling all this information into a single database allows for the analysis of spider distribution in Poland, the assessment of degree of knowledge of individual zoogeographic regions, and also provides opportunity to identify future goals for faunistic research.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The boundaries of zoogeographic regions were adopted in the study based on the *Catalog of Polish Fauna* (BURAKOWSKI *et al.* 1973). The starting point for the analysis of faunistic data regarding spiders found in Poland was the literature lists presented by PRÓSZYŃSKI & STARĘGA (1971) and ROZWAŁKA (2021). Access was obtained to nearly 85% of the publications, and approximately 95% of all estimated faunistic data were entered into the database. The statistics also included data related to historical regions,

such as Silesia or Prussia. For the purpose of analysis, the definition of a faunistic record proposed in GIERLASIŃSKI'S work (2018) was adopted. Maps were generated using the non-commercial MapaUTM ver. 5.4 software (GIERLASIŃSKI 2023).

DISCUSSION

By the end of the 19th century, the number of publications containing faunistic data from the territory of Poland amounted to 65 (PRÓSZYŃSKI & STARĘGA 1971, ROZWAŁKA 2021). The most significant contributions to the knowledge of the country's arachnofauna during that period were the works of FICKERT (e.g. 1874, 1875, 1876), KOCH (e.g. 1870, 1871), KULCZYŃSKI (e.g. 1872, 1876, 1881, 1882a, 1882b, 1884, 1890), NOWICKI (1867, 1868, 1869, 1870, 1874), and subsequent works by MENGE (e.g. 1866, 1868, 1869, 1875). Thanks to these publications, by the end of that century, 491 species were known from Poland, and the number of faunistic records reached almost 6000. Although a significant portion of faunistic data at that time was limited to providing information about historical regions or even just stating the general presence of a species in the country, it is possible to graphically present the records from that period (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The map showing the distribution of faunistic data before 1900 on UTM squares.

Ryc. 1. Mapa ilustrująca rozkład danych faunistycznych sprzed 1900 roku na siatce UTM.

From the beginning of the 20th century until 1945, the amount of faunistic data only slightly increased (by just under 1300 faunistic records), significantly influenced by the political situation in Europe and the ongoing wars. During this time, the number of species known from our country increased to 551 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The map showing the distribution of faunistic data before 1945 on UTM squares (black circles – data before 1900, blue circles – 1901-1945).

Ryc. 2. Mapa ilustrująca rozkład danych faunistycznych sprzed 1945 roku na siatce UTM (czarne kółka – dane sprzed 1900 roku, niebieskie kółka – przedział 1901-1945).

Most of the data from that period concerned the southern part of the country, although even here differences in the level of exploration of individual zoogeographic regions (as defined in the *Catalog of Polish Fauna* (BURAKOWSKI *et al.* 1973)) were evident. This is visible, for example, in the Bieszczady Mts. and Pieniny Mts. regions, where only eleven spider species were documented until 1945. A significant contrast was observed in neighboring regions: the Pomeranian Lake District, from which 170 species were documented at that time, and the Masurian Lake District, where only 17 were known. Equally poorly explored were the Lubelska Upland (15 species), the Małopolska Upland (7 species), the Rostocze Upland (3 species), as well as the Świętokrzyskie Mts., Podlasie Lowland, and Białowieża Forest (0 species).

Only the second half of the 20th century brought significant changes in the understanding of the distribution of spiders in Poland (Fig. 3). Faunistic studies now covered a much larger part of the country. By the end of the 20th century, 778 species of spiders were known from the territories of our country. However, in some zoogeographic regions, the number of documented species still did not exceed 300 (Eastern Beskidy Mts. – 284, Bieszczady Mts. – 296, Nowotarska Dale – 132, Białowieża Forest – 232, Upper Silesia – 284, Tatra Mts. – 269). Compared to the first half of the 20th century, the number of faunistic data concerning the Świętokrzyskie Mts., Podlasie Lowland, the

Fig. 3. The map showing the distribution of faunistic data before 2000 on UTM squares (black circles – data only before 1900, blue circles – data only from 1901-1945, green circles – 1946-2000).

Ryc. 3. Mapa ilustrująca rozkład danych faunistycznych sprzed 2000 roku na siatce UTM (czarne kółka – dane tylko sprzed 1900 roku, niebieskie kółka – dane tylko z przedziału 1901-1945, zielone kółka – przedział 1946-2000).

Masurian Lake District, Roztocze Upland, Lubelska Upland, and Małopolska Upland significantly increased (Fig. 3). The progress in faunistic research is also evident in the increase in records. By the end of 1945, a little over 7000 records came from the works of that time, while in the second half of the 20th century alone, there were over four times as many records (almost 29,000).

Since the beginning of the 21st century, the increase in faunistic data remains substantial (almost 24,000 records in less than twenty-two years) (Fig. 4). However, many areas of our country still have never been studied.

The knowledge of faunal composition is fundamental to research in the field of ecology (zoocenology), zoogeography (including phylogeography), and also provides the opportunity to monitor environmental and climatic changes based on the variability of faunal composition. These studies are currently conducted worldwide, and the results are published in reputable scientific journals. As easily observed, disregarding faunistic research reflects only a lack of understanding of the potential use of the obtained results in a much broader context and the shortsightedness of individuals who depreciate such studies (GIERLASIŃSKI *et al.* 2019).

Fig. 4. The map showing the distribution of all UTM squares with which any faunistic data on Araneae are associated (black circles – data only before 1900, blue circles – data only from 1901-1945, green circles – data only from 1946-2000, red circles – 2001-2022).

Ryc. 4. Mapa ilustrująca rozmieszczenie wszystkich kwadratów UTM, z którymi powiązane są jakiekolwiek dane faunistyczne dotyczące Araneae (czarne kółka – dane tylko sprzed 1900 roku, niebieskie kółka – dane tylko z przedziału 1901-1945, zielone kółka – dane tylko z przedziału 1946-2000, czerwone kółka – 2001-2022).

As noted by Professor LECH BOROWIEC (2023), faunistic traditions in Poland, compared to neighboring countries, are significantly poorer, and the current system for evaluating scientific achievements does not encourage faunistic research. Increasingly, the development of regional studies is being taken over by representatives of the so-called “citizen science”.

The rapidly growing amateur movement currently engaged in faunistic research can be classified as a globally popular form of scientific investigation, in which volunteers collaborate with specialists. This approach is referred to as “citizen science”, and its primary goals are to support science and education (DICKINSON *et al.* 2010). Various projects are currently being implemented, involving the voluntary participation of amateurs, and related publicly accessible platforms allow for the archiving of collected data.

There is no doubt that the development of “citizen science” is driven by the advancement of telecommunication technologies and facilitated access to information gathered in online networks. Until recently, so-called “citizen science” was considered

a marginal phenomenon, of negligible value for the progress of science. Nowadays, no one doubts that the benefits of “citizen science” are immense. Enthusiasts, contributing their passion, time, and funds to research, present a significant opportunity to “rescue” those scientific fields that require the collection of a large amount of data and the involvement of many individuals (DANIELSSEN *et al.* 2005).

One of such fields is faunistics, which relies mainly on results obtained through comprehensive field research. Since, for obvious reasons, it is impossible to engage scientific personnel in costly and relatively unprofitable faunistic studies from the perspective of scientific institutions, the only chance for their development lies in data verified by specialists obtained by amateurs. The vast opportunities that open up before faunists simultaneously impose on them the obligation to support the amateur movement in the scientific “processing” of this data.

FINAL REMARKS

The information contained in the database, forming the basis for the presented analyses, has been made available on the website of the “Spiders (Araneae) of Poland” project (GIERLASIŃSKI & RUTKOWSKI 2023). Since the collection of faunistic records based on available publications, as well as the number of publications themselves, undergoes continuous changes, corrections, and additions, the analyses conducted above will become outdated in the near future. To ensure recipients have continuous access to the current state of knowledge regarding the distribution of spiders in Poland, subsequent supplements and updates will be presented on the mentioned website.

One of the assumptions of the “Spiders (Araneae) of Poland” project is the systematic supplementation of missing information and the addition of further faunistic data from studies that will emerge in the future. In this regard, the author would like to invite researchers willing to share their data to contact him and encourage them to check whether their relevant publications have been fully synthesized on the project’s website. The full list of publications used for the project is currently available at the following address: <https://zbioryprzyrodnicze.web.amu.edu.pl/mapy/publikacje.html>.

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Streszczenie

Badania faunistyczne nad pajakami (Araneae) w Polsce: rys historyczny i perspektywy

W artykule przedstawiono historię badań oraz podsumowano dane faunistyczne dotyczące pajaków występujących w Polsce. Przeprowadzono także analizę stopnia znajomości fauny kraju. Przedstawiono podsumowanie dotyczące liczby gatunków występujących w poszczególnych regionach zoogeograficznych. Omówiono także aktualny stan wiedzy i perspektywy rozwoju nauk faunistycznych w Polsce. Ponadto, w artykule zawarto krótki opis projektu „Pająki (Araneae) Polski” dostępnego obecnie na stronie zbioryprzyrodnicze.web.amu.edu.pl.

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